

Novel Reactions of Cobalt(II) Salts with Dibenzoylmethane and Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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Reactions of cobaltous salts with dibenzoylmethane and nitrogen donor ligands in varied stoichiometric proportions resulted in the formation of a series of complexes of the type $[\text{Co X}(\text{bzbz})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$, $[\text{Co X}(\text{bzbz})\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$, $[\text{Co X}(\text{bzbz})\text{L}_2]$, $[\text{Co X}(\text{bzbz})\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{Co X}(\text{bzbz})_2\text{L}]$, $[\text{Co}(\text{bzbz})\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ClO}_4)$, $[\text{Co}(\text{bzbz})\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)(\text{bzbz})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ (where $\text{X}=\text{Cl}^-$ or Br^- , $\text{bzbz.H}=\text{Dibenzoylmethane}$, $\text{L}=\text{Pyridine}$ or substituted pyridine, $\text{L}'=\text{Quinoline}$ or Isoquinoline and $\text{L}''=2,2'$ -bipyridine or $1, 10$ -phenanthroline). The compounds were characterised and possible stereochemistry deduced on the basis of analytical data, spectra (i. r. and electronic) conductivity and thermal decomposition studies. The compound having the composition $[\text{CoCl}(\text{bzbz})\text{Py}_2]$ exhibits penta coordination of divalent cobalt.

REACTION of cobaltous salt with dibenzoylmethane in alcoholic medium in 1 : 2 molar ratio results in the formation of diaquo bis-(dibenzoylmethanato) Cobalt(II) complex- $\text{Co}(\text{bzbz})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ - upon subsequent neutralisation with ammonia. Several mixed ligand complexes of Cobalt(II)^{1,2}, Cadmium(II)³, Nickel(II)⁴ and Zinc(II)^{5,7} have been reported using ligands containing different donor atoms with varying electronegativities. It was therefore thought worthwhile to investigate the reaction of cobaltous salts with dibenzoylmethane in 1 : 1 stoichiometric ratio in presence of nitrogen donor ligands. In the present communication we report some penta- and hexa coordinated mixed ligand complexes of Cobalt(II) and Cobalt(III) obtained in the present investigation.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of Analar grade and the reactions were studied in absolute alcohol medium.

Preparation of mixed ligand complexes :

1. $[\text{CoX}(\text{bzbz})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)(\text{bzbz})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$:

The compounds of this type were prepared by reacting the solutions of cobaltous salt and dibenzoylmethane in hot ethanol in exactly 1 : 1 molar ratio followed by dropwise addition of ammonia with vigorous shaking.

2. $[\text{CoX}(\text{bzbz})\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$, $[\text{Co}(\text{bzbz})\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ClO}_4)$ and $[\text{CoX}(\text{bzbz})\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$:

These were obtained by adding slightly more amount of the ligand base than required for 1 : 2 ratio to the hot ethanolic solutions of cobaltous salt and dibenzoylmethane (in 1 : 1 ratio) and refluxing the contents for nearly an hour before neutralising the moderately hot solution with ammonia.

3. $[\text{Co}(\text{bzbz})\text{L}''(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$:

Cobalt perchlorate, dibenzoylmethane and the nitrogen donor ligand (bidentate) were taken in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio respectively and the contents were refluxed in ethanolic medium for 2 hours. Then the resulting solution was neutralised by adding ammonia with vigorous shaking.

4. $[\text{CoX}(\text{bzbz})\text{L}_2]$ and $[\text{CoX}(\text{bzbz})_2\text{L}]$:

These were obtained by reacting Cobalt(II) salt and dibenzoylmethane in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio respectively in 200 ml of ethanol in presence of the excess of the ligand (1 : 3). The reaction mixture was kept under reflux for 1 hour. Then air was vigorously drawn through the solution for nearly two hours to get the desired product.

All the isolated complexes were filtered, washed with absolute alcohol several times to ensure complete removal of excess ligand, followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Analyses :

Purity of the isolated compounds was established by estimating metal and halogen by standard methods. In some cases alkaline fusion was found necessary for estimating halogen. Conductance measurements were carried out in $M/1000$ acetone solution using Toshniwal conductivity bridge type CL 0102 with a dip type cell. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on solid specimen using Guoy method. Infrared spectra in the range $5000-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were recorded on nujol mull using Unicam SP-200, Perkin-Elmer and Beckman IR-12 spectrophotometers. The electronic spectra in the visible range were recorded on an Elico model CL 24 spectrophotometer. Thermogravimetric analyses were carried out in a manually

TABLE 1—ANALYSES, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF COBALT(II) AND COBALT(III)

Sl. No.	Compound	Colour	Cobalt(%)		Halogen(%)		Δ_m (mhos)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
			Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.		
1.	[CoCl(bz bz)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	15.78	15.86	9.50	9.54	4.0	4.98
2.	[CoBr(bz bz)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Orange yellow	14.14	14.19	19.18	19.24	3.5	4.91
3.	[CoCl(bz bz)(Py) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	Brick red	11.88	11.93	7.15	7.18	3.8	5.06
4.	[CoBr(bz bz)(Py) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	Orange yellow	10.90	10.95	14.83	14.84	3.5	4.99
5.*	[CoCl(bz bz)(Py) ₂]	Orange red	12.36	12.39	7.40	7.45	8.5	4.82
6.	[CoCl(bz bz)(β -pic) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	Dull yellow	11.22	11.30	6.75	6.80	4.6	5.04
7.	[CoBr(bz bz)(β -pic) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	Orange yellow	10.37	10.41	14.02	14.11	3.5	4.91
8.	[CoCl(bz bz)(γ -pic) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	Orange red	11.26	11.30	6.72	6.80	4.0	5.00
9.	[CoBr(bz bz)(γ -pic) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	Dull orange red	10.38	10.41	14.05	14.11	4.2	4.95
10. ^o	[CoCl(bz bz) ₂ (γ -pic)]	Orange red	9.28	9.30	5.52	5.59	5.8	Diamagnetic
11.	[CoCl(bz bz)(Q)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	12.18	12.31	7.25	7.34	4.4	4.94
12.	[CoBr(bz bz)(Q)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	11.14	11.18	15.08	15.16	3.8	4.96
13.	[CoCl(bz bz)(IQ)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	12.16	12.21	7.28	7.34	3.0	5.08
14.	[CoBr(bz bz)(IQ)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Orange yellow	11.15	11.18	15.06	15.16	2.7	5.02
15.	[Co(NO ₂)(bz bz)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Dull yellow	15.47	15.51	—	—	11.2	4.96
16.	[Co(bz bz)(γ -pic) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂](ClO ₄)	Yellow	9.70	9.76	5.75	5.87	140	5.20
17. ^o	[Co(bz bz)(bipy)(H ₂ O) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	Yellow	8.70	8.75	10.52	10.54	235	Diamagnetic
18. ^o	[Co(bz bz)(Phen)(H ₂ O) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	Orange red	8.58	8.63	10.35	10.40	232	Diamagnetic

* Coordination number is 5. In all other complexes, C.N. is 6.
^o Valency of Cobalt is 3. In all other complexes, valency is 2.

TABLE 2—INFRARED (cm⁻¹) AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA (nm) OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF COBALT(II) AND COBALT(III)

Sl. No.	Compound	ν (C—O)	ν (C—O)	λ_{max} in (nm)		
				ν_1	ν_2	ν_3
	Dibenzoylmethane	1600s	1553			
1.	[CoCl(bz bz)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1605vs	1560vs	500	625	830w
2.	[CoBr(bz bz)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1608vs	1562w	495	615	820w
3.	[CoCl(bz bz)(Py) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	1592vs	1545s	505	635	850w
4.	[CoBr(bz bz)(Py) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	1595vs	1543s	500	624	846w
5.*	[CoCl(bz bz)(Py) ₂]	1590vs	1542s	515(ν_1)	655(ν_2)	870w(ν_3)
6.	[CoCl(bz bz)(β -pic) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	1594vs	1542s	495	625	870br
7.	[CoBr(bz bz)(β -pic) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	1596s	1548m	490	608	865w
8.	[CoCl(bz bz)(γ -pic) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	1588vs	1546s	505	618	850br
9.	[CoBr(bz bz)(γ -pic) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	1590s	1550s	500	600	83br
10. ^o	[CoCl(bz bz) ₂ (γ -pic)]	1592s	1543m	415	675	—
11.	[CoCl(bz bz)(Q)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1593vs	1552s	505	610	830br
12.	[CoBr(bz bz)(Q)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1595s	1545s	500	600	820
13.	[CoCl(bz bz)(IQ)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1592vs	1550s	495	630	832br
14.	[CoBr(bz bz)(IQ)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1594vs	1555s	490	620	825w
15.	[Co(NO ₂)(bz bz)(H ₂ O) ₂]	1610s	1565w	490	645	—
16.	[Co(bz bz)(γ -pic) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂](ClO ₄)	1590vs	1545s	488	625	830
17. ^o	[Co(bz bz)(bipy)(H ₂ O) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	1592vs	1540s	415	705	—
18. ^o	[Co(bz bz)(Phen)(H ₂ O) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	1595vs	1565w	410	680	—

* Coordination number is 5. In all other complexes, C.N. is 6.
^o Valency of Cobalt is 3. In all other complexes, valency is 2.

operated thermobalance. Analyses, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility data are given in Table 1 and infrared and electronic spectral data are included in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The complexes prepared now are either flaky or microcrystalline. Most of the compounds decompose before melting. They are sparingly soluble in most of the organic solvents. The low values of molar conductance Δ_m in acetone medium

for all complexes excepting the perchlorate compounds indicate that they are essentially non-electrolytes. The perchlorate compounds, however are either 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 electrolytes as indicated by their Δ_m values round about 150 and 250 mhos respectively. (See Table 1). The high spin, octahedral Cobalt(II) complexes exhibit μ_{eff} values ranging between 4.8 and 5.2 B.M. indicative of the presence of 3 unpaired electrons with a large orbital contribution. Cobalt(III) ion has a d⁶ configuration and usually forms diamagnetic octahedral complexes. The magnetic susceptibility values of the compounds under report clearly indicate that three of them are

Cobalt(III) complexes and in all the rest divalent cobalt is present.⁸

Infrared Spectra :

Infrared spectrum indicates the presence of the ligand bands but there is a considerable overlapping of bands due to dibenzoylmethane and the nitrogen donor ligand. The bands attributed to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$ are given in Table 2. Definite changes are observed in $\text{C}-\text{O}$ and $\text{C}-\text{C}$ stretching frequencies due to the introduction of the heteroligand atoms. Bands due to the heteroligand are also modified indicating their bonding to the metal ion. The bands due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$ of dibenzoylmethane in these complexes are found to be unaffected. This rules out the possibility of the substitution reaction in the body of the ligand, in which case the composition and the analytical data would have been completely different. In the spectrum of the mixed complexes under study, broad bands are noticed (not given in the table) at $\sim 3450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1650 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ regions which can be assigned to the coordinated water molecule. A broad band arising out of $\nu(\text{Cl}-\text{O})$ was observed in case of perchlorate complexes at $\sim 1090 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating that the perchlorate groups are ionic⁹ but not coordinated. The NO stretching frequency of the nitrate group observed at 1520-1480 and 1305 to 1280 cm^{-1} confirms that the coordinated nitrate group is bidentate¹⁰.

Far-infrared Spectra :

Halogen and the nitrogen base have a tendency to form bridges resulting in polymeric forms. In general bridging $\text{M}-\text{X}$ stretching frequencies are lower than terminal $\text{M}-\text{X}$ stretching frequencies. In the complexes under report Cobalt-halogen and

Cobalt-nitrogen stretching frequencies are observed at ~ 250 and $\sim 220 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively indicating that the compounds are monomers¹¹⁻¹³.

Electronic Spectra :

Cobalt(II) complexes in the octahedral environment should have three spin allowed $d-d$ transitions¹⁴. The bands at ~ 500 , ~ 600 and at $\sim 850 \text{ nm}$ can be assigned to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ (ν_3), ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})$ (ν_2) and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ (ν_1) transitions respectively. The electronic absorption spectrum of hexa-coordinated Cobalt(II) complexes under report is consistent with the octahedral structure¹⁵. The spectrum of only high-spin penta-coordinated Cobalt(II) differs considerably from other hexa-coordinated complexes of Cobalt(II) and shows three bands at 515 (ν_4), 655 (ν_3) and 870 nm (ν_2) showing its resemblance with the known^{16,17} penta-coordinated species. The ν_1 absorption band could not be recorded since it is beyond the range of the instrument used. Octahedral complexes of Cobalt(III) show two principal absorption bands at ~ 415 and $\sim 700 \text{ nm}$ assignable to ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{2g}$ and ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{A}_{2g}$ respectively¹⁸, indicating a distorted octahedral geometry around the metal ion.

Thermogravimetric Analysis :

Thermal decomposition of all the complexes reveals no weight loss at 105° indicating that the water molecules are not in the lattice. It was observed that the compounds of trivalent cobalt directly melt at 200° without decomposition. The pyridine and other similar adducts are observed to decompose according to the following general reactions :—

1. $\text{Co} \times (\text{bzbz})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5(\text{s})$ Yellow	$\xrightarrow{T_1(120-150^\circ)}$	$\text{Co} \times (\text{bzbz})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{s})$ Yellowish green $\downarrow T_2 < 220^\circ$ melts
2. $\text{Co} \times (\text{bzbz})\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{s})$ Red micro-crystalline	$\xrightarrow{T_1(110-130^\circ)}$ $\xrightarrow{T_2(130-150^\circ)}$	$\text{Co} \times (\text{bzbz})\text{L}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{s}) + \text{L}(\text{g})$ Bluish black or Greenish black $\text{Co} \times (\text{bzbz})(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{s}) + \text{L}(\text{g})$ Blue or green $\downarrow T_3 < 200$ melts
3. $\text{Co} \times (\text{bzbz})\text{L}_2(\text{s})$ Orange red microcrystalline	$\xrightarrow{T_1(110-130^\circ)}$	$\text{Co} \times (\text{bzbz})(\text{L}_{3/2})(\text{s}) + \frac{1}{2}\text{L}(\text{g})$ Greenish red $\downarrow T_2 < 150$ $\text{Co} \times (\text{bzbz})\text{L}(\text{s}) + \frac{1}{2}\text{L}(\text{g})$ Green $\downarrow 165^\circ$ melts
4. $\text{Co} \times (\text{bzbz})\text{L}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{s})$ Yellow	$\xrightarrow{T_1 < 150^\circ}$	$\text{Co} \times (\text{bzbz})\text{L}'(\text{s})$ Grass green $\downarrow T_2(170-225^\circ)$ melts

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